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Criteria for Entrepreneurial projects

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INTRODUCTION

In 2015, the Faculty of Engineering Science at KU Leuven chose to put more emphasis on Entrepreneurship in the curriculum [1,2]. A broad definition was used to describe Entrepreneurship: "Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship refers to an individual's ability to turn ideas into action. It includes creativity, innovation, and risk-taking, as well as the ability to plan and manage projects in order to achieve objectives." [3].

Amongst several initiatives to promote entrepreneurship, this paper highlights a new course created to enable students to engage in an entrepreneurial project (i.e., *Entrepreneurship in Practice*).

For the Faculty, this course emphasized the need for well-defined criteria to determine whether a project classifies as “entrepreneurial”. To make a clear difference with other projects offered throughout the curriculum, criteria were defined together with the other Faculties of the Science and Technology Group.

Course evaluation is based upon many factors, with (self-)reflection at its centre. This reflection is thus an important aspect throughout the projects.

This paper first introduces the need for entrepreneurial projects (section 1), then discusses the criteria that define a project as ‘entrepreneurial’ (section 2), as well as the course evaluation (section 3). Finally, some examples of projects are described (section 4) and findings are given (section 5).

1 NEED FOR ENTREPRENEURIAL PROJECTS

During their curriculum, students of engineering take part in many projects. The Faculty of Engineering Science at KU Leuven has more than 10 years of experience in preparing their students for professional practice through a learning pathway called “Problem Solving and Design”. This pathway consists of four courses, spread over the three years of the Bachelor program, in which students collaborate on small project teams on real-life engineering problems.

Major elements of the learning pathway are (1) the different steps of the design process (information gathering, problem definition, generation of ideas, modelling, schematically representing diagrams, calculating and experimenting, evaluation and decision making, and practical realization), (2) reporting, both oral and written communication, and cooperation in a team, and (3) planning and project management [4, 5, 6].

Next to this learning pathway “Problem Solving and Design”, quite a few courses offer projects targeted at applying the theoretical concepts of the course on a practical problem. Some of these projects are made by students individually, some are made in group.

The projects described above focus on many major skills necessary for engineers, but the typical entrepreneurial aspects are not part of their objectives.

In 2014, the Faculty of Engineering felt the need for a more specific focus on Entrepreneurship in the curriculum. Several actions were under taken. (1) The existing Bachelor course *Industrial Management* was reformed, with a focus on Entrepreneurship. The course is now called *Industrial management & Entrepreneurship*. (2) A new elective course in the Master was introduced, focusing on business simulations, strategic management, and creativity and decision making for product development. This is complemented with elective courses offered by the Faculty of Economics & Business.

To turn theory into hands-on experience, the Faculty of Engineering Science created then a new course *Entrepreneurship in Practice* where students can do an entrepreneurial project. The course exists in two variants: a 3 and a 6 credit variant. It

is an elective course which the students can take up from their second bachelor year until their master years. It is the student who has to propose a project. Luckily there are many organizations that offer and coach projects. However, not every project is entrepreneurial. So there was a need for clear criteria to define if a project would fall under the flag of "Entrepreneurial Project". The next section elaborates on these criteria.

2 CRITERIA FOR ENTREPRENEURIAL PROJECTS

The criteria were split in three groups, each again subdivided in subcriteria. The groups are (1) Putting ideas into action, (2) Acquiring resources, and (3) Interdisciplinary work. The following subsections will develop on each of these criteria.

2.1 Putting ideas into action

The first category 'putting ideas into action' (Figure 1) starts directly from the broad definition of entrepreneurship. The project should result in something useful for a target group.

Figure 1

Important is that students talk to real stakeholders. This can be end users, but also local organisations, financial institutions, etc. In regular projects, the role of the stakeholders is often taken by the professor and the assistants. In an entrepreneurial project, however, the student has to go outside the university to find relevant stakeholders. Sometimes surveys are made, or in depth interviews are taken.

In devising what the project could have as output, what “product” (in the broad sense) could be conceived, creativity and innovation are important.

Furthermore, the student has to think about how the product will reach the end users. This can be very elaborate and contain a business plan, but thinking about valorisation in general terms is a minimum. Finally, the sustainability, in the broad sense of the term, is important. Not only the materials used, but the economic sustainability must be discussed. A prototype or mock-up can be made, but is not necessary for all projects.

2.2 Acquiring resources

The second category of criteria (Figure 2) is about acquiring resources. In regular projects, students receive the necessary equipment and software, but are often required to find extra information through literature. In an entrepreneurial project, external advice, coming from outside the university, is often a must. In some projects, financing has to be found, and students write proposals for subsidies from the city or the government. Occasionally, students set up crowd funding.

Important in this category is that students have to take a lot of initiative. Coaches can give leads, but it is the students who have to go outside the university to find the necessary resources for their project.

Figure 2

2.3 Interdisciplinary work

The third criterion (Figure 3) is about interdisciplinary work. All entrepreneurial projects take part in the real world. And the real world is interdisciplinary! Of course the students are educated in one discipline, even if the engineering studies are quite broad. But in an entrepreneurial project, students have to work beyond their own discipline to find out what the consequences are of their choices. We refer here to so called T-shaped professionals.

Figure 3

More specifically, students have to possess deep disciplinary knowledge and be able to function as 'adaptive innovators', crossing the boundaries between different disciplines. In this metaphor, the vertical line of the T represents the depth of the students' disciplinary knowledge and the horizontal line of the T stands for the students' ability to collaborate across a variety of disciplines. To contribute to a creative and innovative process, students have to fully engage in a wide range of activities within a community that acknowledges their expertise in a particular discipline and be able to share information competently with those who are not experts [7].

Ideally, an entrepreneurial project is performed in group, where the different members of the group have a different expertise and background. As our university is a comprehensive university, some projects are carried out by a diverse group of students from engineering, economics, medical doctors, sociologists, ... Such diversity enlarges the added value for all students involved: they learn from each other how students from other disciplines think, and how they tackle problems.

Finally, reflection is crucial. This will be elaborated in the next section, as it is a major part of the evaluation.

3 EVALUATION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL PROJECTS

3.1 Reflection

The following quote underlines the importance of reflection. “We do not learn from experience, we learn from reflecting on experience” [8].

To encourage reflection, students are asked before the beginning of the project to give a list of competences and engineering skills they want to improve during the project. This makes the student reflect on his current capabilities, and on the possible gap between the current situation and his ideal “future self”.

In their report at the end of the project, students make a critical reflection on the competences they wanted to improve. Ideally, students learn things they had not expected to learn. They are asked to reflect on their curriculum, and to show the relation between the project and their study program. Which content of which courses was relevant for the project? Was the course content adjusted to the project needs?

Finally, they have to reflect on the way they have executed the project. Did they make the right choices? Where did they fall short and why?

3.2 Evaluation

The evaluation is based on a written report and an oral presentation. Of course the results of the project, what has been achieved, is assessed. But more importantly, the way the project was executed and the choices were made together with the innovation shown are evaluated. Last but not least, the way the student reflects on his own achievements, on the skills and competences he improved, and on his curriculum, have a large impact on their final grade.

4 EXAMPLES OF ENTREPRENEURIAL PROJETS

This section gives several examples of projects that have been done in the past two years.

4.1 PiP

PiP (Product innovation Project) is an education format where an interdisciplinary team of students works together during a full academic year to come up with a solution for a task given by the project sponsor. This sponsor can be a company, a social organization, a governmental body, ... A PiP-team consists of a mix of students with various backgrounds (engineering, economics, ...). Together they must deliver a working prototype and a business case.

Two concrete examples: (1) The city of Leuven asked a PiP-team to propose a way to enhance the experience of people while shopping. (2) BASF (a large chemical production site) and Microsoft asked a PiP-team how the Microsoft HoloLens technology could improve various trainings or processes at the BASF company. In both cases, the students extensively talked to stakeholders, came up with several ideas, and discussed these with their sponsor. One idea was then chosen, a prototype was developed, and a business plan was drawn.

4.2 Academics for Development

The goal of Academics for Development is to offer students the possibility to contribute to real life issues in developing and developed countries. AFD organizes projects in which a multidisciplinary team of students work together throughout an academic year with a partner organization on an issue that the partner has put forward. During the first phase of the project, the students prepare, analyse, and elaborate with their partner(s) on possible solutions and ideas in Leuven. During the second phase the team is given the chance to implement their ideas and/or solutions on site. The ultimate goal of each project is to realize durable and meaningful social impact.

Two concrete examples: (1) The Poopó lake in Bolivia is suffering through the negative effects of climate change, and the lake is drying up. Catapa, a Belgian NGO, aims at alleviating these negative effects through the collection of rainwater through tanks on local buildings. The AFD-team supports the implementation, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, as well as financing schemes for the overall project. (2) BeeTogether is a project in Tanzania where the AFD-team supports the local bee-keeping sector.

4.3 Academics for Companies

Academics for Companies (AFC) is a student-run organization that does consultancy for companies. Two examples: (1) A market research for the state television into technologies such as Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR). (2) The company Millibeter produces insects to process waste. The company is expanding and needs therefore to relocate. The AFC-team made a full analysis of the problem and drafted a complete logistics plan.

4.4 Self-proposed entrepreneurial projects

Students can also come up with their own ideas. Here is an example.

In the Filia project seniors and students are brought into contact with each other. The students carry out various tasks for seniors ranging from companionship to computer lessons or gardening. The Filia project is a platform that acts as an intermediary in a local community. The project aims at making a prototype platform, marketing plan, and a business plan.

5 FINDING

We found the definition of the criteria very useful, in three different ways. First it helps the students to understand what is meant with an entrepreneurial project, which otherwise would be too vague for them. This clarity encourages students to engage in these projects. Second, quite a few professors of the Faculty of Engineering have doubts about the usefulness of these projects. They believe more in teaching deep technical knowledge. The criteria show them that these projects do not just involve fooling around, but that the learning covers many different important aspects. Lastly, the criteria help the students to reflect, and can be used as a guideline during the oral evaluation.

6 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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